

CASE STUDY: THE SUCCESS OF JAMUN (*Syzgium cumini* L.) IN THE DROUGHT-PRONE DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESHB.Vimala¹ And P.Depthi²1. Scientist (Horticulture), 2. Scientist (Plant Pathology)
Dr.YSRHU-Horticulture Research Station, Rekulakunta, Anantapurvimalabathineni@gmail.com

. (MS Received: 23.01.2023; MS Revised:24.02.2023; MS Accepted: 25.03.2023)

MS 3005

(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE.)

Abstract

There are several types of soil that Jamun grows well in, and it's adaptable to all of them. It thrives even on poor soils without much cultivation. There is no boundary to the growing range of the plant, and it can grow in canyons, degraded areas, calcareous soils, and saline soils. Moreover, it thrives in a pH of 10.5 alkaline soils. However, many serious problems were observed, including falling fruits, flowers, and seed borers that impacted the harvest and quality. Two times at weekly intervals, spraying Potassium Nitrate @ 10 grams plus Boron @ 2g per liter water assists in the early induction of flowers and reduces flower and fruit drop. Lastly, seed borer infestation can be controlled with cyantraniliprole sprayed at 0.1 ml per liter at the early green stage. A higher profit margin can be achieved through efficient input use and less investment. In the drought-prone Anantapur district of Andhra Pradesh, an elderly farmer family reaps great rewards from Jamun.

Key words: Jamun, flowering, Potassium nitrate, seed borer

Introduction

Very recently, the Anantapur district has emerged as the fruit bowl of Andhra Pradesh, becoming the largest producer of various fruits and vegetables. Due to poor monsoons and inconsistencies in rainfall, groundnut, a majorly cultivated crop in the district, experienced losses over the past few decades. In response to this problem, farmers have switched their crops from agriculture to horticulture by utilizing drip irrigation and mulching. Farmers are now able to cultivate almost all types of fruit crops successfully. Under ANGRAU, the Arid Zone Fruits Division under AICRP was established in 1983 to serve the needs of farmers. This division was later attached to Dr.YSRHU in 2007. The Horticulture Research Station, Anantapuramu, which is a part of AICRP, conducts research on arid zone fruit crops, viz., Pomegranate, Aonla, Ber, Tamarind, Custard apple, and Jamun. Additionally, the research station collects and evaluates different germplasm, develops innovative technologies related to pruning, maintenance, fertigation, pest control, and technology transfer to farmers.

As part of the knowledge transfer process, research scientists at Horticulture Research Station, Anantapuramu, have been regularly participating in radio programmes organized by the all-India radio station on 101.7 kHz. As part of this series, one of the research scientists, Bathineni Vimala, exchanged knowledge with farmers through a programme titled "Allaneredu sagu – yajamanyapaddatulu". After listening to this program, the farmers Mr.N.Ramana and Mrs.N.Sumathi, approached the research station and described all the difficulties they were experiencing with Jamun cultivation. The research scientists at the research station offered advice on all of them, from the beginning of flowering to manuring to pest and disease management. By adopting suggested scientific methods in farming, great results have been achieved, and their fortunes have been changed for the better. In the following, we present a detailed success story of the aforementioned Jamun farmers.

Farmers' perspective

Mr. N. Venkata Ramana and Mrs. Sumathi of Raketla (V) in Uravakonda (M) of Anantapur District in Andhra Pradesh practices agriculture. When compared to other crops, Jamun farming is more attractive to them because Jamun plants require less water and maintenance. Furthermore, domestic animals and wild animals do not harm Jamun plants. Proper care and maintenance can extend its lifespan to more than 70 to 80 years. Because of these maintenance benefits, the farmer decided to cultivate Jamun without actually knowing its profitability potential.

Jamun is a tough and harsh fruit that thrives in challenging conditions that are not known to the farmer. Jamun is adaptable and suitable for a wide array of soil types. It thrives even in poor soils with little or no cultivation. The plant can grow in ravines and degraded areas, including saline and calcareous soils. It also sustains in wet

conditions, even in alkaline soils with a pH of 10.5, and is able to withstand continuous inundation for 10-15 days.

Farmyard manure, SSP, and carbofuron granules were added to the top soil, and farmers dug pits of 1x1x1m in size. A single acre could accommodate 40 plants and was spaced 30 feet apart both ways. Anantapur district irrigates most of its crops with drip irrigation. Using drip irrigation can allow farmers in this region to achieve 90 percent efficiency by automating irrigation. At the beginning, it was recommended to water plants every day, but soon it was changed to alternate days. In the district, due to high wind speeds, it is necessary to stack the plants after planting in order to avoid graft joints breaking. In plant basins, fallen leaves act as mulch, and after decomposition they act as manure. Seven years passed before the plants started bearing fruit after they were grown from seedlings. There were around five different sizes of fruit. Many serious problems were observed, including falling fruits, flowers, and seed borers that adversely affected the yielding and quality of the fruit. The farmer experienced the following problems:

1. Pruning of Plants
2. Flowering behavior,
3. Flowers and fruits drop,
4. Infestation due to seed borer.

According to Dr. YSRHU-Horticulture Research Station, Rekulakunta, the plant does not require pruning every year and diseased, crisscrossing dead branches should be removed every year. A more important aspect of pruning is timing, because if the time of pruning misses, sometimes the crop will not be harvested, because flowering occurs on mature twigs 5 to 10 months old. In addition to plucking jamun fruit, the main problem is that the fruit cannot be consumed or marketed once it is dropped from the plant. Therefore, hand plucking is recommended. There should be a reduction in the height of the plant by heading back whenever there is a labor shortage. Early induction of flowering is more important because jamun flowers early; its fruit is available earlier in the market and sells for a higher price. It is recommended that the plant be lowered whenever there is a shortage of labor. The importance of early flowering is significant because jamun flowers early and its fruit is available earlier on the market and sells for a higher price. Upon light irrigation, spraying of 13:0:45 (Potassium Nitrate) @ 10 grams + Boron @ 2g per liter water twice at weekly intervals assists in the early induction of flowers and also reduces flower and fruit drop. Last but not least, seed borer infestation can be controlled by spraying cyantraniliprole at 0.1 ml per liter at the early green stage. This occurs because insect eggs laid at this stage leave red dots on the fruit. After hatching, larvae bore into the seed, deteriorating the quality of the fruit.

Our Research Station, Dr.YSRHU-Horticulture Research Station, Rekulakunta, provides technical information to farmers. We have guided farmers through the process for consecutive two years,

resulting in 18 lakhs and 24 lakhs of rupees in income for farmers. In general, the price per kilogram ranges between 80 and 100 rupees. For every acre of land, investment costs approximately three lakhs. Heavy rains during 2021 and 2022 resulted in some crop losses.

There are approximately 50 seedlings that will bear small fruits weighing roughly 5-8 grams, with more seed weight, which will not be able to be sold to consumers as fruit. On some plants, 400-500 kg

can be harvested. The garden is very diverse. There is a difference between plants that bear early, some that bear shiny fruits, and some that bear high TSS. 270 plants produced profitable yields in the initial year of maintenance, and 50 died as a result of maintenance. So, 270 plants consistently produced profitable yields, with 30 plants yielding small fruits.

Table: 1 Economic returns from the jamun crop

S.No.	Year	Age of the tree	Yield per plant	Yield per 10 acres	Investment	Gross Income	Net Income	B:C Ratio
1.	2020	9 th year	50kg	13.5 tonnes	3,00,000	8,10,000	5,10,000	1.70:1
2.	2021	10 th year	107 kg	22.5 tonnes	3,00,000	18,00,000	15,00,000	5.00:1
3.	2022	11 th year	142 kg	30 tonnes	3,00,000	24,00,000	21,00,000	7.00:1

According to the above table1, the B: C ratio has shoot up from 1.70 to 7.00. Following investment of Rs.3, 00,000 during the year 2020, net income was approximately Rs.5, 10,000/-, followed by Rs.15, 00,000/- in the year 2021 and Rs.24, 00,000/- in the year 2022. Despite the fact that Rekulakunta technology recorded a low B:C ratio (1.70:1) without Dr.YSRHU-Horticulture Research Station, with our technology dissemination, the B-to-C ratio increased to 5:00:1 in 2021 and to 7.00:1 in 2022. In retrospect, it is evident that farmers benefit more from the technological intervention of the Dr.YSRHU-Horticulture Research Station, Rekulakunta.

Conclusion: Dry areas are associated with a number of inherent problems. In spite of this, if modern technologies are applied to a farming system, one can earn a highly successful income. This is if he or she masters the necessary inputs, such as land, labor, capital, and farm management skills. It is therefore possible for farmers to capitalize on the challenges faced in dry areas by turning them into opportunities that bring them happiness and profit. It is recommended

that you approach reliable institutes that work on this crop and can provide you with efficient input use with less investment and a higher profit margin.

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